

Supplementary Fig. S2. Validation of key findings in an additional HER2+ model.

Supplementary Figure S2. Validation of key findings in an additional HER2+ model. (A) Viability of PDX118-derived trastuzumab-sensitive (118TS) and -resistant (118TR) cell lines following treatment with trastuzumab (20 μ g/mL). Viability is expressed relative to vehicle-treated controls, set to 100%. (B) Representative proximity ligation assay (PLA) images showing HER2–CB₂R heterodimers (left) and corresponding quantification of PLA signal (right; $n = 3$). (C–G) Expression of the indicated genes and proteins, as assessed by qPCR (C, E, F) and Western blot analysis (D, G). (H) Representative PLA images of HER2–IFNGR1 complexes (left) and quantification of PLA signal (right; $n = 3$). (I–J) Expression of the indicated genes and proteins determined by qPCR (I) and Western blot (J). (K) Representative PLA images of HER2–HER3 dimers

(left) and quantification of PLA signal (right; $n = 3$). For all PLA images, red indicates PLA signal and blue indicates nuclear staining (DAPI). Scale bars, 50 μm . All data were normally distributed and analyzed using two-tailed two-way ANOVA (A); Student's t -test (B, C, and K); or one-sample t -test (D-J).